

Investigation into the Knowledge, Attitude and Practices of Students Towards Prevention of COVID-19 Pandemic and Family Sustainability Among Students of Federal College of Education (Technical) Akoka, Lagos

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Abstract

The study investigated knowledge, attitude and practices of students towards prevention of COVID-19 pandemic and family sustainability among students of Federal College of Education (Technical) Akoka, Lagos. Three (3) research questions were raised and answered. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study is two thousand one hundred and fifty-three (2,153) respondents with two hundred and fifteen (215) used as sample for the study. The instrument adopted for this study is a structured questionnaire with Likert scale rating which were designed to elicit information relating to the objectives of the study. Results from the findings revealed that students of FCE (T) Akoka had good knowledge of COVID-19 and are ready to share with others (2.50), all questions raised on attitude of FCE(T) Akoka students towards COVID-19 prevention showed a mean above the cutoff point of 2.50 which indicate positive attitude towards the prevention of COVID-19. The study therefore, concluded that respondents had positive responses towards Knowledge, Attitude as well as Prevention (KAP) of COVID-19 which are highly important in curbing and eradicating the spread of the deadly diseases of COVID-19. It was recommended that College Management put an intensive effort towards the provision of essential resources (water, soap, sanitizer, face mask) and educate its staff and students on the importance of immunization against COVID-19 pandemic.

Keywords: Family Sustainability, COVID-19 Prevention, Social Isolation, COVID-19 Protocols, Vaccination

Introduction

Corona virus also referred to as Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus-2 (SARS-CoV-2) causes a severe respiratory disease known as coronavirus disease COVID-19, (Shrikrushna, Bilal, Shubham, Suraj, Shreya, Suraj & Biryani, 2020). COVID-19 was first reported by the World Health Organization (WHO) was announced as a global pandemic on 11th March 2020 (WHO, 2020). The contagious virus began its ravaging effect from Wuhan, Hubei Province, China and then around the world (NCDC, 2020). The surge of COVID-19 in Wuhan, China led to the closure of

public places, halting of public transportation, isolation and management of infected persons, all in a bid to curb the spread of SARS-CoV-2 (Zhong, Luo, Li, Zhang, Liu & Li, 2020). The clinical presentation of COVID-19 symptoms includes fever, fatigue, dry cough, malaise, and difficulty in breathing (Shrikrushna et al, 2020). So far, the disease is characterized by high morbidity and mortality rates (Roy, Tripathy, Kar, Sharma, Verma & Kaushal, 2020) alongside other ailments. The shutting down of social activities throughout the world to mitigate the spread of the

pandemic led to a global lockdown, causing a downturn in global economic fall due to a break in the global supply chain there by affecting family sustainability (Ephraim, Ahmed, Gozzer, Schlagenhaut & Memish, 2020).

Sustainable living simply means making choices and developing habits that are good for the environment. By making intentional choices that are earth-friendly thereby helping improve attitude and practices towards prevention of COVID-19 pandemic. The basic unit of the society is at the household level, and the family share the same living conditions and other basic essential needs and values, the family is therefore at the Centre of any plague that will affect or infect its members causing changes in the way of living. Sustainable Family Development applies the three pillars of sustainable development which are social equity, economic viability, and environmental conservation to families, through a series of family-chosen, family-directed projects which includes family health during COVID-19 era. In helping families reach these goals, Sustainable Family Development help family members support each other in making vital environmental friendly changes in the way of living.

According to Reuben, Danladi, Saleh & Ejembi (2020) prior to the World Health Organization pronouncement of COVID-19 as a global public health challenge and pandemic, many Nigerians regarded the disease as a distant and foreign infirmity that can never spread to Nigeria. It was also in the public domain that COVID-19 is a big man disease. Nigerians, therefore, downplayed the emergence of COVID-19 thereby hesitating the adoption of the initial preventive measures which would have saved costs while protecting the citizenry from undue exposure to the virus. With the confirmation of the index COVID-19 case in Lagos, Nigeria on February 20, 2020, other parts of the country including the north-central region continued their normal routines and social activities without observing the preventive measures initially outlined by Nigeria Centre for Disease Control (NCDC, 2020). With the low level

of education and awareness within some parts of the country, (Ige, 2014), the immediate misinformation on those vulnerable to the disease were expected.

COVID-19 Pandemic in Nigeria has recorded two thousand one hundred and seventeen (2,117) death (Onyeji, 2021). It has been established that an individual could be asymptomatic and not really show COVID-19 symptoms. Going by the way, students go about the COVID-19 safety protocols it therefore becomes worrisome to examine if students possess adequate knowledge, attitude and practice towards prevention of COVID-19 pandemic.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to examine the knowledge, attitude, and practices of students towards prevention of COVID-19 in FCE (T) Akoka. The study specifically:

1. Examine the knowledge of FCE (T) Akoka students towards prevention of the spread of COVID-19.
2. Examine the attitude of FCE (T) Akoka students towards prevention of the spread of COVID-19.
3. Find out the preventive practices of FCE(T) Akoka students towards the prevention of COVID-19.

Methodology

Survey research design was used for the study. The design was used to gather information about variables from a representative sample of the population concerned with ascertaining conditions or strategies that are being used and those that still need to be used to ascertain the knowledge, attitude and practices of students towards prevention of COVID-19 pandemic among students of Federal College of Education (Technical) Akoka, Lagos.

Population of the Study

The population for this study consists of two thousand one hundred and fifty-three (2,153) students of the Federal College of Education (T) Akoka, Lagos in all the programs leading to the Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE). Examination and Record Unit, FCE(T) Akoka, Lagos).

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample for the study comprised of two hundred and fifteen (215) students, constituting 10 percent (10%) of the study population, simple systematic random sampling was used to select students from FCE(T) Akoka Lagos running all programs in Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE).

Data Collection Method

The instrument for collecting of data was a structured questionnaire. The instrument was titled Knowledge, Attitude and Practices Questionnaire (KAPQ). The questionnaire was divided into two sections: A and B, section A was the demographic information of the respondents while section B sought responses for all three objectives. The questionnaire was validated by three (3) experts, two (2) of which are experts from the field of Home Economics and one (1) from Measurement and Evaluation all from Federal College of Education (T) Akoka Lagos. The comments, observations and criticism addressed the face and content value of the instrument. The instrument was reliable as twenty (20) copies of the research instrument were administered to

respondents who were part of the population but not part of the sample under study. The responses were tested using Cronbach Alpha statistics and result of the reliability obtained is 0.76. indicating that the instrument is reliable.

Method of Data Analysis

The data retrieved from the respondents were analyzed using frequency, simple percentage, mean and standard deviation (Descriptive Statistics). The mid-point mean responses of the respondents is 2.50 with which any responses above the mid-point mean was accepted and responses below 2.50 was rejected.

Results

Table 1 shows the mean Responses on the knowledge of FCE (T) Akoka students towards prevention of the spread of COVID-19. Majority of the respondents possess a good knowledge of COVID-19 with mean responses to each of the question far above the cutoff mean of 2.50 Only one item was rejected as regard the source of information about COVID-19.

Table 1: Knowledge of FCE (T) Akoka Students towards Prevention of the Spread of COVID-1

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean
1	I have heard of COVID-19	185	28	1	1	3.85
2	My information about COVID-19 is gotten from social media	20	25	28	142	1.64
3	COVID-19 is the same thing as flu or high fever	65	83	42	25	2.87
4	Viruses are the causes of COVID-19	75	80	40	20	2.98
5	Lockdown throughout the year,2020 was a result of the deadly COVID-19	164	48	3	-	3.75
6	I possess a good knowledge of COVID-19	110	102	3	-	3.50
7	I am ready to share my knowledge of COVID-19 with everyone because it's real	120	86	9	-	3.52

Table 2: Attitude of FCE (T) Akoka Students towards Prevention of the Spread of COVID-19

S/ N	Items	SA (F)	A (F)	D (F)	SD (F)	Mean	Dec.
1.	I have positive attitude towards the adherence to Government Infection Prevention and Control measures as well as to that of the College management	124	88	2	1	3.56	Accept
2.	I wear my face mask regularly to avoid being infected	145	68	2	-	3.67	Accept
3.	I always ensure to keep a distance of 2 meters between me and the next person in the classroom and in crowded places	120	88	7	-	3.53	Accept
4.	Regular hand wash, use of hand sanitizers, social distancing, use of face mask, hand gloves are all part of my new normal life	105	102	8	-	3.45	Accept
5.	Adequate supply and campaign towards protection against COVID-19 is frequently carried out in the College	96	96	21	2	3.33	Accept
6.	It becomes boring, tiring, uncomfortable and even intimidating with the incessant campaign of the use of prevention measures such as use of facemask/face shield, gloves and sanitizers.	86	113	14	2	3.32	Accept
7.	I do have positive attitude towards the use of safety precaution, but unavailability or inadequacy of preventive materials makes usage difficult	102	101	12	-	3.42	Accept

Table 2 indicates the mean responses on the attitude of students towards prevention of the spread of COVID-19. Majority of the respondents agreed to have a positive attitude towards the adherence to the protocols set up by Government Infection Prevention and Control measures (NCDC) as well as that of the college management. Students' wear face mask regularly to avoid being infected, students always ensure to maintain a distance of 2 meters between themselves and the next person in the classroom and in crowded places, regular hand wash, use of hand sanitizers, social distancing, use of face mask, hand gloves are all part of their new normal life, adequate supply and campaign towards protection against COVID-19 is frequently carried out in the college, that it becomes boring, tiring, uncomfortable and even intimidating with the incessant campaign of the use of

prevention measures such as facemask/face shield, gloves and sanitizers and that they have positive attitude towards the use of safety precautions but unavailability, shortage or inadequacy makes usage close to impossible.

Table 3 shows the mean opinion of preventive practices exhibited by FCE(T) Akoka students towards the prevention of COVID-19. The results show that majority of the respondents agreed with the statements that they use face mask frequently, they wash their hands with soap and water frequently, they make use of alcohol based sanitizers where there are no water and soap, that they disagree with anyone who ask them to make use of the nose mask because they can easily forget to come out with it and also uncomfortable wearing, college management is doing their best to ensure safety compliance and curtail

the spread of COVID-19, that they practice social distancing through greetings such as elbow greeting and they ensure strict compliance of COVID-19 safety protocols to

promote healthy living with a mean of 3.41, 3.31, 3.33, 3.00, 3.40, 3.17 and 3.52 respectively which is above the average mean of 2.5.

Table 3: Preventive practices exhibited by FCE(T) Akoka students towards the prevention of COVID-19

S/N	Items	SA (F)	A (F)	D (F)	SD (F)	Mean	Dec
1.	I use my nose mask frequently	102	103	7	3	3.41	Accept
2.	I wash my hands with soap and water frequently	78	126	11	-	3.31	Accept
3.	I make use of alcohol-based sanitizers where there are no water and soap	95	99	17	4	3.33	Accept
4.	I disagree with anyone who ask me to make use of the nose mask because you can easily forget to come out with it and so uncomfortable wearing	54	117	34	10	3.00	Accept
5.	College management is doing their best to ensure safety compliance and curtail the spread of COVID-19	97	107	11	-	3.40	Accept
6.	I practice social distancing through greetings such as elbow greeting	55	126	28	6	3.17	Accept
7.	I ensure strict compliance of COVID-19 safety precautions to promote healthy living	124	79	12	-	3.52	Accept

Discussion of Findings

The study investigated knowledge, attitude and practice of students towards prevention of COVID-19 Pandemic and Family Sustainability among Students of Federal College of Education (Technical) Akoka, Lagos. Result of research question one revealed that the students had adequate knowledge on the prevention of COVID-19 pandemic. This finding corroborates with Reuben, Danladi, Saleh and Ejembi (2020) that collating such information was necessary for the promotion of major preventive behaviors including personal hygiene, social distancing as well as appraising the challenges emanating because of prolonged lockdown and restrictions. Makoni, (2020) reiterated that the prevailing presence of urban slums, dense population, inadequate access to potable water, fragile healthcare system, sharing of sanitation facilities with a high degree of social mixing among the inhabitants of central Nigeria will make the implementation of hygiene and other public health measures necessary for the curbing of the coronavirus impossible.

Research question 3 on preventive practices exhibited by students on the prevention of COVID-19, indicated that majority of the respondents agreed with all the preventive measures, the finding is in direct disagreement with the work of Loannidis, (2020) who asserted that the spread of misinformation and tales regarding COVID-19 and promotion of unscientific traditional treatment in Nigeria jeopardizes the implementation of preventive measures. From the findings of this study, it was discovered that students have the knowledge of the deadly COVID-19 and hence always make use of the facemasks, and hand sanitizers. In addition to the vaccination that was brought into Nigeria and the response it is getting, this will help keep away the increase in the death toll as a result of Covid 19. This finding corroborate the report of NCDC(2021) that that a total of five million seven hundred and twelve thousand and nineteen (5,712,019) Nigerians have been vaccinated against COVID-19 which is a positive practice towards the prevention of

COVID-19 and consequently individual and family sustainability.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study concluded that knowledge, attitude, and prevention is important in curbing and eradicating the spread of the of COVID-19 that is ravaging the whole world.

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made.

1. Students should maintain a positive attitude towards the eradication of any deadly virus, including Covid 19. This can be achieved through personal hygiene, maintaining adherence to the safety protocols such as hand sanitizers, wearing of facemask and maintaining social distancing.
2. College Management should ensure that safety and preventive facilities are functional such as running water, provision of hand sanitizers to students at affordable prices.
3. Government, Health Management Officers (HMOs) and Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) should assist with provision of safety measures items such as face masks and hand sanitizers to ensure individuals maintain personal sanitation and safety.

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